

Effect of Collaborative and Individualized Problem-Solving Strategies on Student Performance in Challenging Biology Concepts in Benue State

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Abstract

This study investigated the effects of collaborative and individualized problem-solving instructional strategy on secondary school students' performance in difficult concepts in Biology in Benue State. Two research questions guided the study while two hypotheses were formulated and tested. The study adopted quasi-experimental non-equivalent pretest and posttest design and population comprised 8,511 senior secondary two students from which a sample of 270 students was selected from six public schools using a multistage sampling technique. Data were obtained using Biology performance test (BPT) and the instrument was variously validated using Kuder-Richardson formula 21 (KR_21). The instrument yielded a reliability of 0.85 and the data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer research questions while analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that there was significant difference in mean performance scores of students taught the same difficult concepts in Biology using collaborative problem-solving instructional strategy and discussion method ($F(1,175) = 483,440; P = 0.000 < 0.05$). Finding also revealed that there was significant difference in the mean performance scores of students taught the same difficult concepts in Biology using individualized problem-solving instructional strategy and discussion method ($F(1,175) = 290.228; P = 0.05$). Based on the findings it was recommended among others that Biology teachers could use collaborative and individualized problem-solving instructional strategy to improve academic performance and problem-solving skills of their students.

Keywords: Collaborative, Individualize, Problem-solving, Performance, Difficult concepts.

Introduction

The importance of science has been recognized all over the world. Adolphus, Alamina and Aderonmu (2013) argued that the economic, technological and social-well-being of nations of the world as well as future development of both human and material resources depend on science. Science is relevant in every facets of life of living organisms. That is why science is valued by the society. The application of science helps to satisfy many basic human needs thereby improving the standard of living of all people. Valenti (2014) emphasized that scientific knowledge in the area of health services has found cure for a number of diseases including cancer. Relatedly, Valenti (2014) asserts that science is often justified to the public as a driving force for huge economic growth which is anchored on the production of clean form of energy. Most of the tools, technologies and medicines we use in the contemporary world are products or by-products of research from pens to rockets and from aspirin to organ transplantation (Jordan, 2012). The gains of science cannot be achieved without proper education of the younger generation. Scientific investigation refers to the relentless effort of scientists to study nature in order to generate new knowledge, make new inventions that can make for a comfortable living of human beings in the society. Science is made up of a body of knowledge and methods which can be transformed into technology to enable man to solve problems that affect life (Novak, 2010). The quality and quantity of science education received by secondary school students are geared towards developing future scientists, technologists, engineers and related professionals (Umar, 2011).

Biology is the science of life of living organisms and their interactions with the environment. Taylor, Green and Stout (2002) defined Biology as the study of life. It is expected that every student should offer one science subject in which case most of the students prefer Biology. This underscores the importance of Biology as key to the study of many other science subjects. The West African Examinations Council (WAEC, 2016) in its report declared that, more students enroll for Biology at senior secondary school level than physics and chemistry owing to its importance. Other reports by the WAEC Chief Examiner have indicated further increase in students' enrollment in Biology over the preceding years (WAEC, 2017; 2018; 2019). Agaba (2013) explains that Biology as one of the courses of study in science education curriculum and a core subject in senior secondary school in Nigeria is very important because it forms the foundation for many fields of study. It is important not only for studying the behaviour of living things, but to benefit human beings and that, it equips the learners with

the basic knowledge and skills that are essential in the study of medicine, pharmacy, nursing, brewing, microbiology and other related disciplines.

Difficult concepts in Biology are those concepts that students cannot understand easily. Students generally experience difficulties in sciences including Biology which most students consider simple because of its low mathematical content (Umar, 2011). Certainly, there are two ways to this. Either the teacher finds such concepts difficult to teach or the students find the concepts difficult to learn. This is why the lack of understanding may not come from students alone but the fact remains that some of the concepts in Biology are not easy to learn. Kyado (2018) outlined ecology, ecosystem, energy flow in nature, cells and organelles, aerobic and anaerobic respiration, tissue respiration, conservation of natural resources, photosynthesis, osmosis, growth, transpiration, kreb's cycle, energy loss in the ecosystem and glycolysis as difficult concepts in Biology. Similarly, Achor and Agbidye (2014) identified some difficult concepts in basic science to include excretion, cells, skeleton, state of matter, measurement and many others. These are all indications that some concepts are actually difficult.

Performance is a multidimensional concept that denotes the process of executing a task or an action and depends on the effectiveness or efficacy of the said task or an action (Ata, Chafik, Razane & Elalami, 2016). Tatjana (2012) argues that performance measurement literature has one common characteristics; it is related to two terms: effectiveness and efficacy; effectiveness as indicator of the degree of a goal attainment and efficacy as indicator of the resources that were consumed to reach the level of performance. The 2018 WAEC report indicated that candidates performed slightly poorer than the previous years with the mean score of 30 and standard deviation of 9.00 as compared with the mean score of 31 and standard deviation of 11.92 in 2017; and that this poor performance has denied many Nigerian students the opportunity of securing admission into higher institutions of learning as well as reducing the manpower need of the nation. Despite this, performance in Biology has remained poor. Johnson, Johnson and Stanne (2008) noted that, collaboration is a philosophy of interaction and personal life style where individuals are responsible for their actions, including learning and respecting the abilities and contributions of their peers. Both collaborative and cooperative learning are anchored on the foundations and ideas of constructivist learning models. While some people may use collaborative and cooperative learning interchangeably, others may use each separately depending on the weight of freedom attached to the meaning.

The process in which the learner constructs his own understanding is what Epstein (2013) referred to as constructivism. Constructivism is a theory of learning which is based on the fact that knowledge is constructed by the learner. This is an approach to learning based on constructivist learning ideologies presented by Piaget in 1965. In this approach, the individual consciously engages in the construction of a product and the utilization of constructivism in education has revealed high-order thinking skills such as problem-solving and critical thinking (Cheng & Liu, 2013). Etiubon (2010) stressed that constructivism is a kind of learning strategy that lays emphasis on active role of learners in the process of constructing their own knowledge. Tauritz (2012) described constructivism as a model of instruction that focuses on the learners' ability to construct his own understanding from experiences and in so doing make meaning to what he learnt. In all cases the teacher is involved and the teacher's ability to make the best use of any of these instructional strategies determines students' participation and their ability to acquire factual knowledge. Eka (2012) opined that, the current thinking about teaching is that, it is an active and constructive process in which the teacher assumes the role of a strategic planner, making decisions about the content and the appropriate instructional strategies. Teachers should therefore make it a duty to ensure that the current best practices are applied in the process of teaching. An individual is also useful in the construction of knowledge. Although sharing of ideas among a number of people could bring about better decisions, individualized way of constructing knowledge can still be useful with proper thinking and reasoning. Central to constructivist perspectives is that a learner constructs meaning from new information and event as a result of an interaction between the individual's alternative concepts and his or her current observation (Ebutu, 2015). Aluko and Olorundare (2017) opined that individualistic instructional strategy is a teaching strategy in which an individual student work alone based on his or her ability using a variety of instructional activities to improve his or her understanding of a subject. This strategy requires each individual to present solution to the subject problem without the cooperation or assistance of other classmates.

Problem-solving is one of the instructional strategies of a constructivist model of learning. Adolphus (2018) asserted that it is a structural education model in which large and small group discussions can be organized. This is a learning model that brings to bear and attempts to relate prior knowledge with that of the actual problem in question. It requires the use of cognitive abilities such as reasoning, thinking, power of observation, discrimination, generalization, imagination, ability to infer and draw

conclusion, try out novel ways as well as experimenting (Adolphus, 2018). Chauhan (2009) asserted that problem-solving is the highest level of learning in the hierarchy proposed by Gagne which depends on the mastery of next types of learning. It involves the application of principles and facts to explain and solve new phenomena and predict consequences from known conditions. Four major steps are involved in problem-solving. These are preparation, incubation, illumination and verification. The process involves preparing, digesting and making efforts to recall and evaluating what has been learnt (Chauhan, 2009). In line with this, Adolphus (2018) explained that the process involves identification of a problem (preparation), definition and exploration (incubation), action (illumination) and look back (verification). Previous studies by Adolphus, Alamina and Aderunmu, 2013; Aluko and Olorundare, 2017 and Thatcher, 2017 have severally demonstrated that collaborative problem-solving learning strategy is suitable for improving learning outcomes in sciences.

Discussion method is an approach to teaching in which the teacher assumes the position of a strategic planner, open up discussion while the students are allowed to also participate in the process. Discussion method is a variety of forum for open ended collaborative exchange of ideas between the teacher and students for the purpose of furthering students' thinking, learning, problem solving, understanding or literacy appreciation. Participants present multiple points of view and respond to the ideas of others while reflecting on their own ideas in an attempt to build their knowledge (Tharp & Gallimore, 2017). In this study, discussion method is adopted as a conventional method to be compared with collaborative and individualized problem-solving instructional strategies as control and not necessarily due to its failure in the past. It is against this backdrop of students' continued failure in examinations that the researcher, faced with the speculation that this gap exists in the use of collaborative and individualized problem-solving instructional strategy to improve knowledge decided to undertake this study which is meant to address the problem in the existence of this gap. The study has solved some problem of instruction while creating an avenue for further study by other researchers. The study therefore provided empirical evidence on the effects of collaborative and individualized problem-solving instructional strategies on students' performance in difficult concepts in Biology at senior secondary schools in the study area.

Various methods and strategies of instruction have been applied in an attempt to improve the teaching and learning of Biology (Ebutu, 2015). Some of such instructional strategies include lecture method,

questioning, discovery method, concept-mapping, discussion and cooperative learning among others. Despite this, performance in Biology has remained poor. As a result of this, it is the concern of stakeholders in education including teachers, curriculum planners, parents and students about the continued poor performance of students in both internal and external examinations in our country. It is therefore necessary to find new ways of improving instruction for the benefit of the learners. Specifically, certain concepts in Biology perceived to be difficult have also contributed to this deteriorating interest and performance of learners as they could not comprehend such concepts. Achor and Agbidye (2014) and Kyado (2018) in separate publications identified ecology, ecosystem, energy flow in nature, cells and organelles, measurement, skeletal system, tissue respiration, cellular respiration, kreb's cycle, energy loss in ecosystem and others as the difficult concepts in science and Biology in particular. What could have been responsible for the continued failure of students in Biology? Could it be instructional strategies that have been applied over the years? It is against this background that Ebutu (2015) advocated for innovative ways of improving the way students learn Biology at senior secondary school level. A number of instructional strategies/methods such as lecture method, discussion method, concept mapping, cooperative learning and many more have been utilized in an attempt to improve learning. The study therefore investigated the varying effects of collaborative and individualized problem-solving instructional strategies on senior secondary two students' performance in perceived difficult concepts in Biology.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study was to find out the effects of collaborative and individualized problem-solving instructional strategies on students' performance in some perceived difficult concepts in Biology, Benue State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Find out the effect of collaborative problem-solving instructional strategy on the performance scores of students in difficult concepts in Biology.
2. Find out the effect of individualized problem-solving instructional strategy on the performance scores of students in difficult concepts in Biology.
3. Determine the difference in performance scores of students taught the same difficult concepts in Biology using collaborative problem-solving instructional strategy and those taught using Discussion method.

4 Determine the difference in performance scores of students taught the same difficult concepts in Biology using individualized problem-solving instructional strategy and those taught using Discussion method.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the difference in the mean performance scores of Senior Secondary two students taught the same difficult concepts in Biology using collaborative problem-solving instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method?
2. What is the difference in the mean performance scores of Senior Secondary two students taught the same difficult concepts in Biology using individualized problem-solving instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses (Ho) were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of Senior Secondary two students taught the same difficult concepts in Biology using collaborative problem-solving instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of Senior Secondary two students taught the same difficult concepts in Biology using individualized problem-solving instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method.

Methodology

This study adopted a quasi-experimental research design; specifically a non-equivalent control group involving a pretest-posttest was used. Because of the quasi-experimental nature of this research, it is not feasible to randomly compose and group students as this will also bring about the disturbance of already existing class arrangement. The intact classes in the sampled schools were therefore used. Quasi-experimental design is a school friendly design which does not disrupt the structures of already existing classes. Githae, Keraro and Wachanga (2015), explained that, an important component of quasi-experimental study is the use of pretest or the analysis of prior knowledge achievement to

establish group equivalence and that, if it is not possible to randomly sample and assign subjects to groups, the researcher can use intact classes.

The sample for this study comprised 270 SS II students that offer Biology in six schools selected from Benue Educational Zone C using multi-stage sampling technique. The number of students for experimental group was 180 while that of control group was 90. The schools were selected based on public schools and grant aided schools where there are experienced teachers of Biology. The samples were based on six intact classes with one class each from the six schools. At the first stage, purposive sampling technique was used to isolate all the co-educational schools offering Biology as a subject. Secondly, two schools were selected from each of the old districts within the zone using simple random sampling technique of hat and draw giving a total of six schools. The process involves assigning numbers to designed cards which were reshuffled and the selection was done by drawing cards from them to identify schools selected. Thirdly, the selected schools were randomly assigned to the three groups, which were two experimental and one control through hat and draw method. In the fourth stage, simple random sampling technique was used to select one intact SSII class in each of the schools which helped to avoid inter-group interaction. The students in the first experimental group were taught using collaborative problem-solving instructional strategy and the second experimental groups were taught using individualized problem-solving instructional strategy while the control group was taught using discussion method of instruction. One main instrument was developed and used for this study by the researcher. The instrument was Biology Performance Test (BPT). The BPT which was adapted from past West African Examinations Council (WAEC) questions between 2010 and 2019 and modified comprises 40 items multiple choice questions with option of letters A – D; drawn from the topics of Ecology, Ecosystem, Energy flow, cell as well as cellular organelles. The BPT was administered to 20 SSII students each and their scores was subjected to reliability test using Kuder Richardson formula - 21 (KR₂₁). The BPT yielded a reliability coefficient (r) of 0.85. The instrument was therefore considered reliable for this study, and to have good internal consistency. According to Musa (2017), a reliability test shows acceptable level of internal consistency if the value is greater than 0.50. Mean scores and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 significant level. The choice of ANCOVA was based on the fact that the study used a quasi-experimental design of pretest posttest to

determine the equivalence of the experimental and control groups and to take care of the possible lack of initial equivalence in groups, since intact classes were involved.

Results

Research Question One: What is the difference in mean performance scores of Senior Secondary two students taught the same difficult concepts in Biology using collaborative problem-solving instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Performance Scores of Students Taught Biology using Collaborative Problem-solving Instructional Strategy and Discussion Method

Strategies		PreBPT	PostBPT	Mean gain
Collaborative problem-solving instructional strategy	Mean	38.00	76.71	45.64
	N	90	90	
	Std. Deviation	12.37	5.40	
Discussion Method	Mean	34.07	59.78	25.71
	N	90	90	
	Std. Deviation	7.26	6.84	
Mean difference				19.93

Table 1 shows the difference in the mean performance scores of Senior Secondary two students taught the same difficult concepts in Biology using collaborative problem-solving instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method. The Table shows that 90 students were taught Biology using collaborative problem-solving instructional strategy and 90 students were taught using discussion method. The Table reveals that the mean performance scores of students taught Biology using collaborative problem-solving instructional strategy was 38.00 with standard deviation of 12.37 during pre-test and 76.71 with standard deviation of 5.40 in post test. While the mean performance scores of students taught Biology using discussion method was 34.07 with standard deviation of 7.26 during pre-test and 59.78 with standard deviation of 6.84 in post test, Table 1 further shows that the mean gain of students that were taught Biology using collaborative problem-solving instructional strategy was 45.64 and those of students taught Biology using discussion method was 25.71. The difference in the mean performance scores of Senior Secondary two students taught the same difficult concepts in Biology using collaborative problem-solving instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method

was 19.93 in favour of students taught Biology using collaborative problem-solving instructional strategy.

Research Question Two: What is the difference in Mean performance scores of Senior Secondary two students taught the same difficult concepts in Biology using individualized problem-solving instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Performance Scores of Students Taught Biology using Individualized Problem-solving Instructional Strategy and Discussion Method

Strategies			PreBPT	PostBPT	Mean gain
Individualized problem-solving instructional strategy	Mean		36.67	76.50	39.83
	N		90	90	
	Std. Deviation		7.25	7.26	
Discussion Method	Mean		34.07	59.78	25.71
	N		90	90	
	Std. Deviation		7.16	6.84	
Mean difference					14.12

Table 2 shows the difference in the mean performance scores of Senior Secondary two students taught the same difficult concepts in Biology using individualized problem-solving instructional strategy and discussion method. The Table shows that 90 students were taught Biology using individualized problem-solving instructional strategy and 90 students were taught using discussion method. Table 1 further reveals that the mean performance scores of students taught Biology using individualized problem-solving instructional strategy was 36.67 with standard deviation of 7.25 during pre-test and 76.50 with standard deviation of 7.26 in post test. The mean performance scores of students taught Biology using discussion method was 34.07 with standard deviation of 7.16 during pre-test and 59.78 with standard deviation of 6.84 in post test, Table 2 further shows that, the mean gain of students that were taught Biology using individualized problem-solving instructional strategy was 39.83 and those of students taught Biology using discussion method was 25.71. The difference in the mean performance scores of Senior Secondary two students taught the same difficult concepts in Biology using

individualized problem-solving instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method was 14.12 in favour of students taught Biology using individualized problem-solving instructional strategy.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of Senior Secondary two students taught the same difficult concepts in Biology using collaborative problem-solving instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method.

Table 3: ANCOVA of Performance Scores of Students Taught Biology using Collaborative Problem-Solving Instructional Strategy and Discussion Method

Dependent Variable: PostBPT

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared	Eta
Corrected Model	19051.685 ^a	4	4762.921	124.763	.000	.740	
Intercept	64956.202	1	64956.202	1701.504	.000	.907	
Collaborative	52.969	1	52.969	1.388	.240	.008	
Gender	.521	1	.521	.014	.907	.000	
Strategy	18455.689	1	18455.689	483.440	.000	.734	
Gender*Strategy	22.763	1	22.763	.596	.441	.003	
Error	6680.759	175	38.176				
Total	893788.000	180					
Corrected Total	25732.444	179					

a.RSquared=.740 (Adjusted R Squared=.734)

Table 3 reveals that $F(1,175) = 483.440$; $p = 0.000 < 0.05$. Since p is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there was a significant difference in mean performance scores of Senior Secondary two students taught the same difficult concepts in Biology using collaborative problem-solving instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method. Thus, it can be concluded that there was a significant difference in mean performance scores of Senior Secondary two students taught the same difficult concepts in Biology using collaborative problem-solving instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method. The partial Eta square of 0.734 was obtained for the strategies meaning that 73.4 percent of students' performance in difficult concepts in Biology can be attributed to the strategies employed in Biology classes.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of Senior Secondary two students taught the same difficult concepts in Biology using individualized problem-

solving instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method. Table 4: ANCOVA of Performance Scores of Students Taught Biology using Individualized Problem-Solving Instructional Strategy and Discussion Method

Dependent Variable: PostBPT

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	13995.163 ^a	4	3498.791	73.213	.000	.626
Intercept	39742.129	1	39742.129	831.608	.000	.826
Individualized	452.543	1	452.543	9.470	.002	.051
Gender	6.656	1	6.656	.139	.709	.001
Strategy	13869.856	1	13869.856	290.228	.000	.624
Gender*Strategy	12.030	1	12.030	.252	.616	.001
Error	8363.164	175	47.790			
Total	850739.000	180				
Corrected Total	22358.328	179				

a. R Squared = .626 (Adjusted R Squared = .617)

Table 4 reveals that $F(1,175) = 290.228$; $p = 0.000 < 0.05$. Since p is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there was a significant difference in mean performance scores of Senior Secondary two students taught the same difficult concepts in Biology using individualized problem-solving instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method. Thus, it can be concluded based on evidence from data analysis that there was a significant difference in mean performance scores of Senior Secondary two students taught the same difficult concepts in Biology using individualized problem-solving instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method. The partial Eta square of 0.624 was obtained for the strategies meaning that 62.4 percent of students' performance in difficult concepts in Biology can be accounted for, by the strategies employed in the teaching of Biology.

Discussion of Findings

Findings of this study are discussed in this section. Discussion of findings was tailored along the variables in the study as guided by the answers to research questions and test of hypotheses. The study

investigated the effects of collaborative and individualized problem-solving instructional strategies on secondary school students' performance in some difficult concepts in Biology. Findings revealed that there was significant difference in the mean performance scores of Senior Secondary two students taught the same difficult concepts in Biology using collaborative problem-solving instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method. This means that the use of collaborative problem-solving instructional strategy has enhanced students' performance scores more than the discussion method. This finding agrees with that of Hsin-ke and Peng-chun (2017) that the post-test scores of experimental group using collaborative instructional strategy were significantly better than the pre-test. Finding also agrees with that of Gokhale (2010) that the mean scores of the group that studied collaboratively were higher than the group that studied individually and ANCOVA yielded a significant difference. However, the finding disagrees with that of Achor and Agbidye (2014) that no significant difference in the mean achievement of those who perceived concepts as difficult and those who perceived them as not difficult. Some of the perceived difficult concepts included excretion, cells, skeleton, state of matter, measurement etc. Others that were perceived not difficult are feeding, respiration, growth, reproduction and pollution.

The collaborative problem-solving instructional strategy has been effectively utilized for the purpose of instruction in Biology class to help enhance students' performance as evident in the significant difference found in the present study. This is because the use of collaborative problem-solving instructional strategy builds the learners' skills in problem-solving and critical think ability. The use of collaborative problem-solving instructional strategy also allows Biology teachers to divide the students into groups with students of different level of abilities using a variety of instructional activities to improve their understanding. The findings was that there is significant difference in Mean performance scores of Senior Secondary two students taught the same difficult concepts in Biology using individualized problem-solving instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method. This means that Biology could be better taught using individualized problem-solving instructional strategy than discussion method. The finding agrees with that of Adeyemi and Cishe (2016) that treatment on individualistic instructional strategy had significant main effect on students' achievement over the conventional lecture method. The finding also agrees with that of Kyado (2018) that there is significant

effect of individualized instructional strategy in students' achievement in Biology than those of conventional lecture method.

Conclusion

The use of collaborative and individualized problem-solving instructional strategies enhanced students' performance in Biology. These strategies have enhanced the learning of Biology because they are learner friendly and have created opportunity for active participation of students with the teacher serving as a guide. The effects of these strategies have shown that performance in Biology is a function of method. Since Biology can be studied both in classroom and field, it is necessary to pay greater attention to the use of collaborative and individualized learning where students participate actively. The implications of the findings therefore, are that collaborative and individualized problem-solving instructional strategies enhanced students' performance and problem-solving abilities in Biology as a subject. It was concluded that collaborative and individualized problem-solving instructional strategies were of great benefits to all students

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations were made:

1. Biology teachers should be trained by government through the Ministry of Education on the use of collaborative and individualized problem-solving instructional strategies both in teacher training institutions and in-service training programmes
2. Biology teachers should use collaborative and individualized problem-solving instructional strategies more frequently to improve academic performance and problem-solving skills of their students in Biology.
3. Publishers of Biology textbooks at the secondary school level should incorporate these strategies for teaching various aspects of Biology especially the identified perceived difficult concepts in Biology.

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